

**Comparative Analysis of Teachers' Job Performance in Private and Public Secondary Schools in Ilorin
East Local Government, Kwara State**

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Abstract

The study examined the difference between teachers' job performance in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State. Descriptive research design of survey type was employed in the study. The population of the study comprised all SSS three students in the 40 public and 36 private secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State. Twenty public secondary schools and 18 private secondary schools were proportionately sampled, this represented 50% of each school type. Ten students were randomly selected from each of the sampled schools to make a total of 380. Researcher-designed questionnaire titled "Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire" (TJPQ) was used to collect data. The instrument was validated. Reliability of the instrument was ensured using Cronbach's Alpha and coefficient of 0.68 was realised. T-test was used to test the hypotheses. Out of the 360 copies of the questionnaire distributed, only 327 were filled, returned and used for analysis. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant difference between teachers' job performance in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State. Based on the findings of the study, teachers in public secondary schools should be more committed to their job performance while private secondary school teachers should not rest on their oars, in order to facilitate effective realisation of the school goals.

Keywords: Teachers' Job Performance, Student Assessment, Classroom Management, Instructional Materials

Introduction

Teachers are not only cerebral but also the tripod upon which education rests, irrespective of the level. If teachers are up and doing in the performance of their job, instructional objectives as well as the general school goals are likely to be well achieved but otherwise might be the case if duties of teachers are carried out haphazardly. According to Ismail et al. (2020), job performance refers to the degree at which a worker contributes to the achievement of the organisational goals. It is gauged based on the organisational set goals and the extent to which an individual employee has contributed to their realisation. In education, job performance refers to the extent to which teachers carry out the official tasks assigned to them such as lesson plan preparation, student assessment, classroom management, records keeping and lesson presentation.

Igukor (2018) defined job performance as the measure of the delivery of teachers' official duties, primarily aims at realising the school goals. This has to do with the manner in which a teacher uses acquired skills in carrying out the official duties in achieving the established goals. Owan (2018) elucidated job performance as the degree to which teachers discharge their pedagogical and instructional assignments, for students to be able to acquire knowledge and for the school to attain its objectives. Aron et al. (2019) affirmed that the extent to which a school achieves its established objectives could be determined by how teachers perform their job. Oluoma et al. (2021) explained that job performance means the statutory duties discharged by teachers, in order to realise the school goals. Yakubu et al. (2020) opined that the yardsticks for measuring job performance of teachers include preparation of lesson plans and lesson notes, students' records keeping, classroom management, effective lesson delivery, student assessment and engagement in students' extracurricular activities. The aspects of job performance examined in this study are instructional materials, student assessment and classroom management. Olaniyan (2017) believed that the success of Nigerian secondary schools, like other levels of education, is anchored on high teachers' commitment to the performance of their official duties in the aspects of classroom management, records keeping, mastery of the subject matter, teaching methods, utilisation of instructional material, and participation in co-curricular activities. The aspects of job performance examined in this study are utilisation of instructional materials, student assessment and classroom management.

Obinaju (2016) stated that instructional materials are the resources utilised by teachers to enhance better clarification of concepts taught and make learning understandable to students. Lawal (2020) submitted that instructional materials are crucial tools essentially required for teaching and learning, in order enhance effective actualisation of instructional goals. They make learning more realistic, practical, interesting, appealing and facilitate improved acquisition of knowledge, skills and the development of self-actualisation and self-confidence. Abidoye and Abidoye (2023) maintained that instructional materials are teaching materials which educators utilise while imparting knowledge to students, in order to facilitate effective understanding of lessons.

Abidoeye et al. (2022) explained that instructional resources help teachers to convey knowledge in an attractive way in making learning more fascinating, as they assist students in better acquisition of knowledge. The findings of Esu et al. (2016) revealed that instructional materials are very important to the effective teaching and learning activities and also aid successful lesson presentation to learners in schools. Therefore, instructional materials are very essential to learning and help students to acquire better knowledge and skills.

According to Sadler (2019), assessment refers to the process used by teachers during instructional delivery period in getting feedback on the success of an ongoing teaching and learning, in order to improve students' achievement in lessons. Authur (2017) elucidated assessment as the means utilised by teachers to determine the success which they have made in teaching students certain contents of learning. The significance of assessment in education cannot be underrated because it helps in educating students, parents and students about the students' progress in education, over a period of time. Nathaniel (2015) opined that assessment is used to determine the extent to which the instructional objectives of a particular lesson has been actualised. Not only that, it is also a means of discovering the students' strengths and weaknesses during learning process. Taylor (2016) believed that assessment means the process of measuring, evaluating and recording the progress of learning and skills acquisition of students in a particular teaching and learning process. The essence of carrying out assessment for students is to ascertain whether or not the predetermined goals in education have been realised. Obilor (2019) viewed assessment as a systematic way of getting information on what a learner knows, can do, and what is learning to do. Through the information derived in assessment, teachers, principals or government would be able to make decision on planning for improvement in teaching and learning. Ogbonnaya (2014) viewed classroom management as the process of providing favourable conditions for regulating the social behaviour of students while the business of teaching and learning is ongoing. The behaviours exhibited by learners are greatly determined by the manner in which teacher handles management of classroom. Miwari and Eleberi (2020) explained classroom management as the act of using varied techniques and skills by teachers, in order to make students attentive, orderly, focused and productive during instructional delivery process. When classroom management is effectively done, there could be minimal display of behaviour that would impede effective learning. Nwankwo (2018) stated that classroom management contributes significant roles to the success of teaching and learning process. It is an important aspect which teachers do not need to play with while imparting knowledge to students. Sunday et al. (2022) posited that classroom management is the process of organising and conducting the activities of classroom using various skills, in order to facilitate actualisation of instructional objectives. It includes designing and conserving the environment of classroom in a manner which would facilitate effective learning, as well as realisation of lesson's goals. Ezemba et al. (2021) believed that attainment of the goals of education, among other things, is determined by the effectiveness of teachers' classroom management. Teachers are managers and such, there is need for them to possess effective managerial skills

which would make them have full control of students, in order to achieve their desired goals in imparting knowledge to students.

Statement of the Problem

Job performance of some teachers in public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State seemed not encouraging, as reflected by the researchers' first-hand knowledge and information gathered from some principals, vice principals, students and parents. Some teachers in these schools do not prioritise the use of instructional materials despite its role in facilitating effective teaching and learning; some do not give students assignment as a way of engaging them in learning at home while some give but do not mark it; and their classroom management is not worthwhile due to nonchalant attitude. Based on the abysmal scenarios observed in some public secondary schools, the researchers decided to compare their job performance with that of their counterparts in private secondary schools in the local government area. Some researchers have conducted studies related to this study. Ogundele and Olanrewaju (2014) investigated the influence of teachers' jobs satisfaction on the job performance of secondary schools in Kwara State. Elijah and Ekwesianya (2020) carried out a study to ascertain the relationship between principalship, decision making and teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Adeyemi (2020) conducted analysis of teachers' job performance of teachers in private and public secondary schools in Ijumu Local Government, Kogi State, Nigeria. However, none of these studies compared job performance of teachers in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government and this is the gap which this study filled.

Objectives of the Study

The study:

- i. examined the difference between teachers' job performance in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State;
- ii. determined the difference between teachers' student assessment in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State;
- iii. assessed the difference between teachers' classroom management in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State; and
- iv. investigated the difference between teachers' use of instructional materials in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State.

Research Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between teachers' job performance in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between teachers' student assessment in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between teachers' classroom management in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State.

H₀₄: There is no significant difference between teachers' use of instructional materials in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State.

Methodology

The study examined the difference between teachers' use of instructional materials in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State. Descriptive research design of survey type was employed in the study. The population of the study comprised all SSS three students in the 40 public and 36 private secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State. SSS three students alone were considered as the population because they had completed two academic sessions in their respective schools and this gave them opportunity to give adequate information about their teachers. Twenty public secondary schools and 18 private secondary schools were proportionately sampled, this represented 50% of each school type. Ten students were randomly selected from each of the sampled schools to make a total of 380. Researcher-designed questionnaire titled "Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire" (TJPQ) was used to collect data from the participants of the study.

The instrument had segment A, B and C (that is, Student Assessment, Classroom Management & Use of Instructional Materials) and each segment had six items. The instrument was validated by one expert in the Department of Educational Foundations, School of Education, Federal College of Education, Iwo, Osun State; and two lecturers in the Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education, University of Ilorin, Ilorin. Reliability of the instrument was ensured using Cronbach's Alpha and coefficient of 0.68 was realised. This confirmed the suitability of the instrument for use in the study. T-test was used to test the hypotheses. Out of the 380 copies of the questionnaire distributed, only 347 were filled, returned and used for analysis.

Results

Hypotheses One: There is no significant difference between teachers' job performance in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State, Nigeria.

Table 1

Difference in the Teachers' Job Performance in Private and Public Secondary Schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State

School type	N	\bar{X}	SD	Calculated t-value	p-value	Decision
Public	193	2.46	.70	1.38	.031	Rejected
Private	154	3.90	1.27			

Table 1 shows calculated t-value (1.38) and the p-value (.031) which is less than the significance level (0.05). Hence, hypothesis one is rejected. This depicts that there was a significant difference between teachers' job performance in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State.

Hypotheses Two: There is no significant difference between teachers' student assessment in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State, Nigeria.

Table 2

Difference in the Teachers' Student Assessment in Private and Public Secondary Schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State

School type	N	\bar{X}	SD	Calculated t-value	p-value	Decision
Public	193	2.62	.84	1.43	.014	Rejected
Private	154	3.93	1.11			

Table 2 shows calculated t-value (1.43) and the p-value (.014) which is less than the significance level (0.05). Hence, hypothesis two is rejected. This signifies that there was a significant difference between teachers' student assessment in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State.

Hypotheses Three: There is no significant difference between teachers' classroom management in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State, Nigeria.

Table 3

Difference in the Teachers' Classroom Management in Private and Public Secondary Schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State

School type	N	\bar{X}	SD	Calculated t-value	p-value	Decision
Public	193	2.49	.51	1.25	.016	Rejected
Private	154	4.16	1.40			

Table 3 shows calculated t-value (1.25) and the p-value (.016) which is less than the significance level (0.05). Hence, hypothesis three is rejected. This means that there was a significant difference between teachers' classroom management in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State.

Hypotheses Three: There is no significant difference between teachers' use of instructional materials in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State, Nigeria.

Table 4

Difference in the Teachers' Use of Instructional Materials in Private and Public Secondary Schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State

School type	N	\bar{X}	SD	Calculated t-value	p-value	Decision
Public	193	2.27	.74	1.33	.012	Rejected
Private	154	3.62	1.29			

Table 4 shows calculated t-value (1.33) and the p-value (.012) which is less than the significance level (0.05). Hence, hypothesis four is rejected. This signifies that there was a significant difference between teachers' use of instructional materials in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State.

Discussions

The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant difference between teachers' job performance in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State. The mean score (3.90) of

private secondary schools which is greater than the mean score (2.46) of public secondary schools shows that job performance of teachers in private schools was better than that of public schools. This finding agrees with the finding of Adeyemi (2020) that there was a significant difference between job performance of teachers in private and public secondary schools in Ijumu Local Government, Kogi State, Nigeria. In addition, the finding supports the assertion of Bamigbose (2020) that the manner in which teachers in private secondary schools in Nigeria perform their job is more effective than the way their counterparts do in public secondary schools.

The findings of the study showed that there was a significant difference between teachers' student assessment in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State. The mean score (3.93) of private secondary schools which is greater than the mean score (2.62) of public secondary schools shows that teachers' student assessment in private schools was better than that of public schools. This finding corroborates the finding of Ademola (2019) that there was a significant difference between students' assessment in public and private secondary schools, Ogbomosho South Local Government, Oyo State. This finding is in tandem with the position of Jaiyeola (2020) that ineffective assessment of students has been very common in public secondary schools in Nigeria. As a result of this, there is need for adequate monitoring of teachers' job performance in public schools, in order to make their dedication to students' assessment effective like that of teachers in private schools.

The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant difference between teachers' classroom management in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State ($p > .05$). The mean score (4.16) of private secondary schools which is greater than the mean score (2.49) of public secondary schools shows that teachers' classroom management in private secondary schools was better than that of public schools. This finding agrees with the finding of Adeyemi (2020) that there was a significant difference between classroom management in private and public secondary schools in Ijumu Local Government, Kogi State, Nigeria. This finding also supports the position of Bamigbose (2020) that classroom management of some teachers in public secondary schools in Osun State is not appealing cannot be compared with that of their counterparts in private schools.

The findings of the study showed that there was a significant difference between teachers' utilisation of instructional materials in private and public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State ($p > .05$). The mean score (3.62) of private secondary schools which is greater than the mean score (2.27) of public secondary schools shows that teachers' student assessment in private schools was better than that of public schools. This finding is in consonance with the finding of Adeyemi (2020) that there was a significant difference between teachers' utilization of instructional materials in private and public secondary schools in Ijumu Local

Government, Kogi State, Nigeria. This means that utilisation of instructional materials is better in private than public secondary schools.

Conclusion

The study concluded that teachers' job performance in private secondary schools was better than that of public secondary schools in Ilorin East Local Government, Kwara State, Nigeria. Specifically, student assessment, classroom management and utilisation of instructional materials of private secondary school teachers were better than that of public secondary schools.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

- i. teachers in public secondary schools should be more committed to their job performance while private secondary school teachers should not rest on their oars, in order to facilitate effective realisation of the school goals;
- ii. teachers in public secondary schools should prioritise students' assessment more while private secondary school teachers should not relent in their efforts of assessing students, so as to properly determine the areas of strengths and weaknesses of students in learning;
- iii. public secondary school teachers should intensify efforts in the classroom management so as to meet and also surpass that of their colleagues in private secondary schools, in order to have always achieve a well-controlled classroom environment required to achieve instructional objectives; and
- iv. instructional materials utilization should be given more priority by teachers in public secondary schools like their colleagues in private secondary schools do, in order to enhance better assimilation of lessons.

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